

MODAPTO [101091996]: Modular Manufacturing and Distributed Control via Interoperable Digital Twins

D2.1 - Dissemination and Communication Strategy

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Executive Summary

This document is the MODAPTO deliverable D2.1 “Dissemination and Communication Strategy” that includes the actions relevant to T2.1 “Communication, Industrial and Scientific Dissemination”. This document sets out the dissemination and communication strategy as well as the plan to raise awareness, share knowledge, and attract potential stakeholders in the context of the MODAPTO project, through various means. These means include the MODAPTO website, the use of Social Media, the distribution of communication material, publications in scientific journals, participation in conferences & other relevant events and organisation of workshops and demonstrations with potential end-users. The report provides a comprehensive framework for actions that will support outreach efforts necessary to disseminate and communicate the achievements and benefits of the MODAPTO project. It provides a focused dissemination & communication approach towards the key target audiences and the best approaches to engage and inform stakeholders to maximise knowledge of MODAPTO activities.

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List of Terms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ARK	Archival Resource
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTs	Digital Twins
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
PID	Persistent Identifier
Purl	Persistent uniform resource locator
SME	Small-medium enterprise
T	Task
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WP	Work package
WPs	Work packages

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This dissemination & communication strategy provides a comprehensive framework for actions that will support outreach efforts necessary to disseminate and communicate the achievements and benefits of the MODAPTO project. It provides a focused dissemination & communication approach towards the key target audiences and the corresponding channels to reach them most effectively as well as the timing of these activities and the partners responsible for their implementation. As the European Union distinguishes between dissemination and communication, we also support this distinction and provide a detailed definition of the meaning of both dissemination and communication in the context of MODAPTO. This enables the reader to gain a clear understanding of both the difference and overlap between the two concepts in terms of audiences and channels when combining them into an overall strategy, as presented in the subsequent chapters of this deliverable.

1.1.1 Definition & Scope of Communication within MODAPTO Project

The European Commission (EC) has defined communication as *"the means of taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The purpose is to reach out to society as a whole and specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges"*.

In light of this definition, communication within the MODAPTO project will encompass all efforts to inform the audience about the project, its activities, and its results. This includes communication about the project as a whole, such as its general description, consortium partners, objectives, approach, and other relevant information. Furthermore, communication will also include disseminating specific project results, facts, and figures, as well as communication about upcoming events and project activities. In short, communication will play a crucial role in raising awareness about MODAPTO, its goals, and the impact it aims to achieve.

1.1.2 Definition & Scope of Dissemination within MODAPTO Project

According to the EC, dissemination is the active process of promoting and raising awareness about the results of a project to various stakeholder groups, including research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, and policymakers. It involves public disclosure of project results in any medium and enables stakeholders to use the outcomes in their own work.

Within the MODAPTO project, we interpret dissemination as a process of actively disseminating project results to different stakeholders through various channels. These channels include scientific publications such as conferences and journals, project workshops, webinars, and online repositories of project results and data.

To ensure that our dissemination efforts align with the guidelines set by the EC for Horizon Europe actions, the consortium follows their guidance on how to communicate and promote the project. We also emphasize the importance of open access to research results and data, in line with the EC's open access policy and open access repository guidelines.

To promote open access to project results, MODAPTO will publish all public project deliverables, outcomes, and raw research data on the project website, (<https://modapto.eu/>) Moreover, we will use open-access repositories such as Github (<https://github.com/>), Gitlab (<https://about.gitlab.com/>), OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>) or Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) to ensure that our scientific publications and research data are freely accessible to all stakeholders.

1.2 Relation to other Work Packages and Deliverables

The activities and the final outcome of WP2 “Dissemination, Exploitation, Business & Knowledge Transfer” and more specifically of Task 2.1 “Communication, Industrial and Scientific Dissemination” are highly dependent on receiving inputs from all work packages, tasks and deliverables of MODAPTO project. In this deliverable, all project partners have contributed in building the dissemination and communication plan and the results of other WPs will be presented and communicated, via WP2. The most important outcomes of every WP will be presented to a wider audience through the current WP, via dedicated meetings and specific dissemination and communication templates. Finally, every project’s public deliverable will be reaching the ‘outside world’ via the activities of WP2. Therefore, the activities described in this document are in high dependence on the activities of all the WPs and the corresponding Deliverables.

1.3 Methodology and Structure of the Deliverable

This strategy is a living document involving all the partners, with regular updates along with the project’s periodic reports. The updated plans will list the dissemination and communication activities implemented and planned. In addition, all final dissemination and communication activities of the project will be reported in deliverable D2.2 “Dissemination and Communication Report” in month 36.

This deliverable is structured as follows for the remaining chapters.

- Chapter 2 presents the dissemination & communication strategy. More specifically, the dissemination and communication objectives of the project are mentioned as well as the dissemination and communication phases to reach the target audience and achieve the strategy’s objectives are defined.
- Chapter 3 analyses the target stakeholders and audiences, addresses the appropriate channels for approaching the target groups, and describes the individual stakeholders to be reached.
- Section 4 provides a detailed description of the dissemination and communication channels/activities.
- Chapter 5 describes the design and establishment of the project’s visual identity.
- Chapter 6 outlines the dissemination and communication time plan of the project.
- Chapter 7 provides a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the communication and dissemination activities while describing and estimating their impact. An analysis of risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project is also presented.
- Chapter 8 describes the roles and responsibilities of all partners engaged in the dissemination and communication activities.
- Finally, Chapter 9 concludes this deliverable.

2 MODAPTO Dissemination & Communication Strategy

2.1 Objectives

MODAPTO envisions flexible industrial systems that are composed of production modules enhanced by distributed intelligence via interoperable Digital Twins (DTs) based on industrial standards, seamlessly integrated within a common framework that enables coordination with other modules and systems. At the same time, MODAPTO materializes the benefits of global production view by enabling collective intelligence within modular production schemes for effective module and production line design, reconfiguration and decision support. More specifically, MODAPTO aims to:

- Develop a Toolkit for Optimal Modular Production and Reconfiguration;
- Facilitate seamless module integration by advancing DT standards & interoperability;
- Support decisions for sustainable modular production through collective and distributed intelligence;
- Develop novel sustainability capabilities for new production modules;
- Offer proof-of-value for sustainable modular manufacturing;
- Support the adoption of sustainable modular manufacturing;
- Devise novel business models and strategies for the modular manufacturing domain.

Toward this end, MODAPTO central dissemination & communication objectives are to:

- Provide visibility and public awareness of the project by following a strategy targeting the critical actors in the broader European community and national public bodies;
- Publish results in international industrial and academic conferences, workshops and journals to inform the relevant interested third parties (academic/research and private/public organisations) about MODAPTO;
- Support cluster collaboration and cross-pollination;
- Promote SME engagement and provide workforce and trainers' training for knowledge transfer.

2.2 Dissemination & Communication Phases for the Project

The dissemination and communication activities of MODAPTO results will differ in intensity based on the evolution of the project. The dissemination and communication activities will be carried out in three main phases, spanning throughout the project's duration and extend beyond it, with increasing level of intensity, starting from the creation of general awareness and concluding with attracting through workshops potential stakeholders and users of the project results. The three phases are presented in Table 1, as follows.

Table 1: Dissemination & Communication Phases

Phase	Objectives	Type of Information	Dissemination & Communication Channels/Activities
Phase I	Inform & Connect: Create	Approach-oriented content; project	Use traditional & online communication channels (project website, press releases,

Phase	Objectives	Type of Information	Dissemination & Communication Channels/Activities
	awareness about the project.	presentation; objectives; expected results.	<p>social media, postings, flyers, newsletters etc.);</p> <p>Open access publications in scientific journals, publications in general printed/online media, participation in events and international conferences to gain insights from and better links to manufacturing and industrial communities;</p> <p>Creation of project video;</p> <p>Organization and participation in clustering activities with other EU projects in order to establish a core cluster, discuss cross-fertilisation and the implementation of joint activities;</p> <p>Industrial partners' network.</p>
Phase II	Demonstrate & Contribute: Promote the novel services & show cases; Engage target users & early adopters in the project activities.	Result-oriented content; project intermediate results.	<p>Project website & Social Media; Press releases, newsletters, flyers;</p> <p>Open access publications in scientific journals, publications in general printed/online media, participation in events and international conferences;</p> <p>Further and continuous action will be taken in Clustering activities exploiting synergies between the projects and increasing their impact. Common areas of collaboration will be agreed and actions will be taken in identified areas which address similar technology needs;</p> <p>Synergies with EU Initiatives as well as with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms;</p> <p>Disseminate the MODAPTO outcomes to student conferences.</p>
Phase III	Share & Convince: Leverage the exploitation of the outcomes.	Result-oriented content; project final results and lessons learnt.	<p>Project website & Social Media; Press releases, newsletters;</p> <p>Open access publications in scientific journals, publications in general</p>

Phase	Objectives	Type of Information	Dissemination & Communication Channels/Activities
			printed/online media, participation in events and international conferences; Clustering activities; Synergies with EU Initiatives as well as with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms; Workshops and demonstrations with potential end-users, training material and demos; Industrial community intranet; Disseminate the MODAPTO outcomes to student conferences.

The timing of the phases has been adjusted based on the ongoing work in the project relating to what has already been accomplished and what is yet to come. This means that phases are overlapping and partially parallel as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dissemination and Communication Phases within the Project Time plan

2.2.1 Phase I: Inform & Connect (M1-M36)

In this early phase of the project there are two main goals for the communication and dissemination activities. One is to concentrate on making the project known among its different target audiences. The other is to connect audiences around the world for input and collaboration.

Making the project known among the target audiences is key to creating awareness for the project, getting people on board and interest them in the work. Communicating the project objectives, concepts, specifications as well as research findings will be key tasks to achieve this.

This can best be done through channels like the project website, press releases, newsletters and events participation. But also, through the use of multiple social networks like Twitter and LinkedIn, through which we will be able to spread information about the project and connect to experts and interested individuals and groups.

The “Inform & Connect” phase extends over the whole project’s lifetime. Creating a network of high influencers in the areas of the project will be a main goal of this phase, but also raising general awareness of the project, proclamation of project goals, concepts and research findings among researchers and target users.

2.2.2 Phase II: Demonstrate & Contribute (M18-M36)

The second communication and dissemination phase is all about demonstrating progress of the project and getting people to contribute to the work. This involves future users of the **MODAPTO** framework & tools, Manufacturing SMEs as well as scientific experts from other (EU / research) projects for collaboration. Building on a successful first phase of communication, this can best be achieved by using the established connections and networks. Presenting early achievements of the project will work as calls-to-action, asking audiences for feedback and ideas, but also showing them how the project progresses. It is very important to have first components or examples to share with the audience. These should be accompanied by explanations from technical partners describing the current state of technical developments and future steps.

To successfully implement this phase, it is necessary to have adequate feedback channels in place, through which users can reply. Social media channels are a great way for this, as well as a contact form on the website and a project-email should be established for this.

First steps of the “Demonstrate & Contribute” phase will be taken already during the first year (e.g. awareness of the project to other projects) since its concepts do overlap with the “Inform & Connect” phase. The first real activity however will not start until the first results are available and the technical direction of the project is clear. These activities will continue until the end of the project. The dissemination efforts will be focused on providing use case results, samples and feedback channels.

2.2.3 Phase III: Share & Convince (M30-M36)

The third phase of the dissemination and communication strategy will coincide more or less within the third year of the project. The focus in this phase will be on sharing achieved results and on convincing end users to test and start using the **MODAPTO** framework & tools. The main dissemination activity in this phase will have two main focuses.

- **User focus:** Showcasing the **MODAPTO** solution and engaging with early users to get feedback on the outcomes of the **MODAPTO** project.
- **Technical focus:** Sharing project results and testing the technical **MODAPTO** solution, showcasing different modules and cutting-edge technologies developed, etc.

These activities take place at various events, conferences or workshops. They are also provided through marketing material on the website and through the different established social media channels (where applicable).

The success of these dissemination efforts depends on stable results of the project.

2.2.4 Final integration towards end of project and beyond

Before completely wrapping up the project, it will be crucial to evaluate the connections made during the project's duration in order to get beyond the mere project status. With a successful **MODAPTO** solution at hand, gaining further collaborators and even a continuation of the development of the **MODAPTO** solution is a lot easier. Communication will at this point aim at presenting the successful results of the consortium's work as well as at winning stakeholders who see potential in the project's results.

Of course, in order to share a convincing message, it is absolutely crucial to have a working prototype/ integration of the **MODAPTO** solution that can be presented to possible collaborators and interested groups. Using the established channels, the progress and success of the project will be communicated, aiming at a broad audience as well as at particular interest groups. One central part of this will be the website and the connected social media channels. Another one should be direct contacts through conferences, workshops and demonstrations with potential end-users including presentations of the results.

All these activities are already part of phase 3, only gaining a special focus once the official project end and the final evaluation is near. Ideally the communication of the project and its results continues beyond the official end, which depends very much on the results and their tangibility and usability.

3 Target Audience

3.1 Defining the audience for MODAPTO

Effective dissemination & communication is essential to keep stakeholders well informed, motivated and keen to participate. In order to ensure that there is the maximum impact of dissemination & communication, it is worth considering:

- **Who is the key audience?**
- **What are the specific messages to be conveyed and the desired outcome?**
- **Are the means of communication appropriate?**
- **How can the effectiveness of dissemination and communication be evaluated?**

Consideration of these points will support the development of a clear dissemination and communication strategy, maximizing impact and ensuring the appropriate stakeholders are engaged.

Thus, all stakeholders must be identified and categorized, from people with the greatest involvement, through to more peripheral individuals or groups. The more important the stakeholder is to the success of the project; the more time and resources will be needed to devote to maintain their involvement and commitment.

All partners will use synergies in their own networks and target further relevant stakeholders at regional, national, EU and international levels, and Horizon Europe projects that could be integrated into the clustering activities. The partners will primarily focus on the communities which are the closest to the project scope and expected results, e.g. automotive, engineering, etc. A preliminary list of relevant stakeholders has been identified:

- Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain;
- SMEs in the modular manufacturing domain;
- ICT innovators-companies;
- Research community-Academia;
- Industrial Community;
- Food Industries;
- Standardization and Regulatory Bodies;
- Professional Associations and Industry Groups;
- Business Model Developers;
- Student Groups in relative university departments;
- Horizon Europe projects;
- EU Initiatives, Technology or industrial clusters, associations and platforms.

In order to target these different audiences and stakeholders in an efficient way, it is best to address each audience through its appropriate channels. For example, the best way to connect to a scientific audience is probably within a conference. Keeping that in mind, the MODAPTO project suggests the following channels- in relation to the different types of audience defined beforehand (Table 2).

Table 2: Approaching Target Groups

Target Group	Channel/Activity	Main direction for messages
<p>Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain</p>	<p>Project website Social Media Events and presentations Flyers and newsletters International conferences and stands Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms Training material and demos Workshops and demonstrations Articles in printed/online media Press releases Video Industrial community intranet Industrial partners' networks</p>	<p>How the outcomes of the project will help them to identify solutions for day-to-day operations; What breakthroughs should their company benefit from; Which transformation steps are required within their plant.</p>
<p>SMEs</p>	<p>Project website Social Media Events and presentations Flyers and newsletters International conferences and stands Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms Training material and demos Workshops and demonstrations Articles in printed/online media Press releases Video</p>	<p>How the outcomes of the project will help them to identify solutions for day-to-day operations; What breakthroughs should their company benefit from.</p>

Target Group	Channel/Activity	Main direction for messages
<p>ICT innovators-companies</p>	<p>Industrial community intranet Industrial partners' networks</p> <p>Project website Social Media Flyers and newsletters International conferences and stands Synergies with EU Initiatives Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms Training material and demos Workshops and demonstrations Articles in printed/online media Press Releases Video Industrial community intranet Industrial partners' networks</p>	<p>What is the innovation of the project; How this can be used and further exploited; Open access of project results.</p>
<p>Research community-Academia</p>	<p>Project website Social Media Flyers and newsletters International conferences and stands Open access publications in Scientific Journals Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects Synergies with EU Initiatives Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms Workshops and demonstrations</p>	<p>What are the research, technological and industrial breakthroughs of the project; What is the innovation of the project; How these can be used and further exploited; Open research questions and steps ahead; Open access of project results for academic purposes.</p>

Target Group	Channel/Activity	Main direction for messages
	<p>Articles in printed/online media</p> <p>Student conferences</p> <p>Press Releases</p> <p>Video</p>	
<p>Industrial Community</p>	<p>Project website</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Events and presentations</p> <p>Flyers and newsletters</p> <p>International conferences and stands</p> <p>Synergies with EU Initiatives</p> <p>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</p> <p>Training material and demos</p> <p>Workshops and demonstrations</p> <p>Articles in printed/online media</p> <p>Press Releases</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Industrial community intranet</p> <p>Industrial partners' networks</p>	<p>What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How this can be used and further exploited;</p> <p>Open access of project results.</p>
<p>Food Industries</p>	<p>Project website</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Events and presentations</p> <p>Flyers and newsletters</p> <p>International conferences and stands</p> <p>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</p> <p>Training material and demos</p>	<p>How the outcomes of the project will help them to identify solutions for day-to-day operations;</p> <p>What breakthroughs should their company benefit from.</p>

Target Group	Channel/Activity	Main direction for messages
	<p>Workshops and demonstrations</p> <p>Articles in printed/online media</p> <p>Press releases</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Industrial community intranet</p> <p>Industrial partners' networks</p>	
Standardization and Regulatory Bodies	<p>Events and presentations</p>	<p>What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How this can be used and further exploited;</p> <p>How should standardization include emerging technologies and new operation methods.</p>
Professional Associations and Industry Groups	<p>Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects</p> <p>Open access publications in Scientific Journals</p> <p>Events and presentations</p> <p>International conferences and stands</p> <p>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</p> <p>Workshops and demonstrations</p>	<p>What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How this can be used and further exploited;</p> <p>Open access of project results;</p> <p>Gain knowledge and insights into modular manufacturing, distributed control, and digital twins.</p>
Business Model Developers	<p>Open access publications in Scientific Journals</p> <p>Events and presentations</p> <p>International conferences and stands</p>	<p>Development of business models facilitating the transferability of the MODAPTO Project to other sectors.</p>
Student Groups in relative university departments	<p>Student conferences</p>	<p>What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How this can be used and further exploited;</p>

Target Group	Channel/Activity	Main direction for messages
		Which research topics could be deployed around the project's results; Open access of project results.
Horizon Europe projects	Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects Project website Social Media Events and presentations International conferences and stands Workshops and demonstrations Open access publications in Scientific Journals Industrial community intranet Industrial partners' networks	What is the innovation of the project; How can this be linked to previous projects' outcomes; How this can be used and further exploited; Which fields of common interest exist in sister projects; How is a technology area evolving and addressed by community tendencies; Open access of project results.
EU Initiatives, Technology or industrial clusters, associations and platforms	Open access publications in Scientific Journals Events and presentations International conferences and stands Synergies with EU Initiatives Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms Workshops and demonstrations Industrial community intranet Industrial partners' networks	What is the innovation of the project; How this can be used and further exploited; Open access of project results; Gain knowledge and insights into modular manufacturing, distributed control, and digital twins.

3.2 Reaching Target Audience

Table 3 below provides an initial list of key stakeholders. This list will be expanded during the project period.

Table 3: Indicative Target Audiences

Name	Short Description	Type	Website
RENAULT-NISSAN-MITSUBISHI MOTORS Alliance	French-Japanese strategic alliance between the automobile manufacturers <u>Renault</u> , <u>Nissan</u> and <u>Mitsubishi Motors</u> , which together sell more than 1 in 9 vehicles worldwide	Manufacturing companies in the automotive domain for which modularity is important to support vehicles diversity production	https://alliancerenm.com/
CONTINENTAL TIRE	A leading company in the domain of tire manufacturing	Manufacturing companies in the Tire domain for which modularity is important to support tire diversity production	https://www.continental-tyres.co.uk/
Siemens AG	Siemens AG is an engineering and manufacturing company. The Company focuses on areas of electrification, automation, and digitalization. Siemens, particularly its Digital Industries division, could use the MODAPTO project to enhance its manufacturing processes and possibly incorporate the technology into its industrial automation and digitalization solutions	Manufacturing Companies	https://www.siemens.com/global/en/products/automation.html
SCHNEIDER ELECTRIC	Schneider Electric SE is a French multinational company that specializes in digital automation and energy management. It addresses homes, buildings, data centers, infrastructure and industries, by combining energy technologies, real-time automation, software, and services. As a Firm that works with digital twin technology and industrial automation, SE might find value in MODAPTO's approach to creating interoperable digital twins based on industrial standards.	ICT Innovators (Engineering Services), Manufacturing companies in the domain of electrical components production for which modularity is required to configure the process to each component to be produced	https://www.se.com/w/en/
Nestlé	Nestlé is the world's largest food and beverage company with a wide range of products from coffee, dairy products, to	Food Industry	https://www.nestle.com/

Name	Short Description	Type	Website
	<p>prepared dishes and cooking aids. Given Nestlé's vast and diverse production lines, the company could benefit from MODAPTO's toolkit to increase production flexibility, streamline processes, and enhance sustainability efforts. Implementing the Digital Twin technology could further optimize production and decision-making processes.</p>		
International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)	<p>As the body responsible for IEC standards, they may be interested in the MODAPTO project as it aims to contribute to the standardization process</p>	Standardisation Body	https://www.iec.ch/homepage
EFFRA	<p>The European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA) is a non-for-profit, industry-driven association promoting the development of new and innovative production technologies.</p>	Professional Associations & Industry Groups	https://www.effra.eu/
Bain & Company	<p>Bain could help companies to build business models that integrate MODAPTO's digital twin technology for optimizing manufacturing operations.</p>	Business Model Developer	https://www.bain.com/
IFAC CC5	<p>Research community in manufacturing - Coordinating Committee on Cyber-Physical Manufacturing Enterprise - composed of TC5.1., TC5.2., TC5.3. & TC5.4</p>	Research Community working of different aspects of modular, adaptable, flexible, reconfigurable manufacturing	https://tc.ifac-control.org/5
CIRP	<p>Research community in manufacturing - Composed at least of STC A and STC O addressing MODAPTO issues</p>	Research Community working of different aspects of modular, adaptable, flexible, reconfigurable manufacturing	http://www.cirp.net
SMES in the Piedmont region	<p>Industries similar to Iltar interested in the application of DTs to their processes</p>	SMEs in the modular manufacturing domain	https://www.confindustriacanavese.it/menu/gruppi/piccola-industria/

Name	Short Description	Type	Website
FSDET	A leading student conference developed in Athens University and Economics, Greece	Student Groups in relative university departments	https://fsdet.dmst.aueb.gr/
Altechna Coatings	One of the largest optical engineering company in the eastern and central region of the European Union, focused on the development and in-house production of optical coatings and components for laser systems, and optical devices targeting leading Original Equipment Manufacturers	Industrial Community	https://www.altechna.com/
Soli Tek Cells	SoliTek develops, produces and installs sustainable glass glass and glass foil solar panels, for the rooftops of any kind, integrated into buildings (BIPV) or stand-alone on the ground.	Industrial Community	https://www.solitek.eu/en
Optoman	Designs, develops, and manufactures high damage threshold laser optics	Industrial Community	https://www.optoman.com/
DuKubu	Hi-tech company that integrates cutting edge technologies to create automation and robotics products	Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain	https://www.dukubu.lt/
Cluster of Manufacturing Innovators - CoMI	Provides access to laboratories about latest technologies that are available in all major Lithuanian industrial cities, which is especially needed at the early stage of creating innovations in the regions.	EU Initiatives, Technology or industrial clusters, associations and platforms	https://klaster.lt/en/klasteris/innovative-manufacturing-cluster/
Linde+Wiemann (Supplier to the automotive industry)	Global acting suppliers / plant operators in the automotive	Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain	https://www.linde-wiemann.com/en/
Allgaier (Supplier to the automotive industry)	Global acting suppliers / plant operators in the automotive	Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain	https://www.allgaier-group.com/en
Volkswagen (Original manufacturer, OEM)	Global acting original equipment manufacturers / plant operators in the automotive (future: other	Manufacturing Companies in the modular	https://www.volkswagengroup.com/

Name	Short Description	Type	Website
	industries, e.g. aerospace) domain	manufacturing domain	
BMW (Original manufacturer, OEM)	Global acting original equipment manufacturers / plant operators in the automotive (future: other industries, e.g. aerospace) domain	Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain	https://www.bmwgroup.com/en/company.html
Stellantis	Engagement with top management and stakeholders to disseminate the project achievements at global level the project along Stellantis's very large automotive group, which is a community of approximately 300,000 employees, with a presence in more than 130 countries, with manufacturing facilities in 30 countries all around the world	Manufacturing Companies in the modular manufacturing domain	www.stellantis.com

4 Dissemination-Communication Channels/Activities

The MODAPTO consortium makes use of a variety of dissemination and communication channels/activities. Table 4 below outlines the dissemination and communication channels/activities that are deployed by the MODAPTO consortium and show how these help increase the impact of the project.

Table 4: Dissemination-Communication Channels/Activities

Channel/Activity	Description	Benefit of the Channel/Activity
Website	<p>Establish online presence – a website where the interested parties can read about the project progress and findings;</p> <p>Create an online repository on the website for anyone to download project findings and public deliverables.</p>	<p>The project website is a key instrument for enhancing the visibility of the project;</p> <p>Project website clearly refers visitors to the MODAPTO vision and educates them about the project concept;</p> <p>All project findings are published on the website to allow anyone interested in the subject to follow the progress of the project.</p>
Industrial community intranet	To establish an industrial community intranet.	The online platform will provide members of the industrial community with exclusive access to project documentation and demos, fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and engagement among community members.
Social Media	<p>Create a Twitter account and a LinkedIn Page for sharing project news, events, resources, demonstrations, publications and reach people that are interested in the outcomes of the project; Create a YouTube channel for promoting project videos and related activities;</p> <p>Use consortium social networking contacts (Twitter, LinkedIn) to reach out to a wide range of communities.</p>	Social media are fast, low cost channels of reaching interested groups and communities that are normally not present at any events, conferences.
Industrial partners' networks	Disseminate the results of new production modules with novel sustainability capabilities and disseminate the objectives and	Sharing of the project results with the SMEs will increase the visibility of the project UCs highlighting

Channel/Activity	Description	Benefit of the Channel/Activity
Flyers	disseminate results of the application of modular DTs obtained during the project to the SMEs.	the project's innovations and their potential applications.
	Create flyers with key project public information to be distributed at events and downloaded from the MODAPTO website.	Project flyers distributed at various events, conferences, workshops etc. gain the project visibility with the general public.
Newsletters	Distribute online Newsletters to all stakeholders to inform them about project progress and findings.	Project newsletters show the progress of the project to all stakeholders and keep their interest high.
International conferences and stands	Submission of Abstracts and Full papers relevant to the scientific progress of the project (for peer-reviewed academic conferences). Stands and exhibitions in industrial conferences.	Peer reviewed academic conferences will provide an academic dissemination of the project outcomes to the specific audience and enable cross validation of the outcomes. For industrial conferences the benefits include a wide dissemination of the outputs of the project and further collaboration and lead generation for potential customers.
Open access publications in Scientific Journals	Submission of full papers relevant to the scientific progress of the project (for peer-reviewed scientific journals). Publishing Open Access means making publications available free of charges, therefore available online for all the persons interested in it.	Peer reviewed scientific journals will provide an academic dissemination of the project outcomes to the specific audience and enable cross validation of the outcomes. The benefit of Open Access publications in Scientific Journals is the sharing of results connected with the MODAPTO project, favoring the science progress through accessible literature to every interested stakeholder
Synergies with EU Initiatives	Finding establishing and fostering collaborations and synergies with	Finding relevant synergies will allow to leverage

Channel/Activity	Description	Benefit of the Channel/Activity
Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms	relevant European Union (EU) initiatives that align with the goals and objectives of the project, and maintaining active relationship by involving other project into MODAPTO activities.	existing resources, knowledge, and networks to enhance its impact and contribute to the broader EU framework.
Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects	New partnerships with relevant national or regional initiatives, funding programs, and platforms that might develop into new funding opportunities, joint projects, and knowledge exchange activities.	Finding relevant synergies will allow to leverage local resources, expertise, and funding opportunities to enhance the project's impact and facilitate knowledge exchange.
Training-demos	The objective of clustering activities is to increase the technical and social impact of the MODAPTO results on European level; this will be possible thanks to the collaboration and technical discussions with other EU projects. To develop and make available online training materials and specific demos related to the MODAPTO project.	The clustering activities with other EU project can allow the advancing of cooperation and exchanging of knowledge contributing to the success and the positive impact of the involved projects. Training-demos will provide valuable resources to interested parties, including stakeholders, professionals, researchers, and the broader community, to enhance their understanding and practical knowledge of the project's concepts, technologies, and lessons learned.
Workshops and demonstrations	The showcase of technologies and solutions developed by the project partners in the context of MODAPTO. The workshops will be hosted by technological project partners.	The workshops and demonstrations will provide hands-on experiences and practical insights to industry partners, stakeholders, and interested parties, highlighting the project's innovations and their potential applications.

Channel/Activity	Description	Benefit of the Channel/Activity
Articles in printed/online media (not scientific)	Articles (and white papers) in industrial magazines relevant to the technologies of the project	A focused communication of the project outputs for specific target audiences that are subscribed to the various outlets.
Student conferences	Paper abstracts, Full papers, panels, workshops with material relevant to the project outcomes	A wide dissemination to undergraduate and post graduate students in disciplines relevant to MODAPTO.
Press Releases	Publish Press releases to highlight project results in English at European/International level.	Press releases can target specific stakeholders depending on the channel where press release is published and can communicate in a regular basis the newest achievements of the project and keep the audiences up to date.
Video	A project video showcasing the project challenges and objectives in a non-technical and self-explicative way as possible in order to reach the widest audience.	A project video on MODAPTO concept and results helps make the results more obvious, thus appealing to a more generic non-technical audience. A video is a powerful tool for attracting key stakeholders.

The rest of this chapter describes in more detail each dissemination and communication channel/activity.

4.1 Project Website

Objective	To spread information about the project’s activities and results a dedicated project website has been created (https://modapto.eu/) with links to the social networking sites that the project is utilising. The project website is also a repository to store the project-produced content as well as public deliverables of the project.
Content and Messages	Project’s objectives, results, impact, partner information, resources (material, public deliverables, publications), and a blog with news and events.

Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Main project documentation and material; medium-level detail
Information Provider	All Partners for the dissemination activities that undertake in the framework of the project
Communication Methods	Communication Material, Newsletters
Activities	Gathering documentation, editing and regularly publishing content and news on the website
Schedule	Key revisions every six months updating throughout the project's duration (news and events updated on an ad-hoc basis)
Monitoring	ATC is responsible for monitoring volume of traffic on the site and providing statistics via Google Analytics.
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for building, hosting and maintaining the project website.

4.2 Industrial community intranet

Objective	To establish an industrial community intranet platform. This dedicated online platform will provide members of the industrial community with exclusive access to project documentation and demos, fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and engagement among community members.
Content and Messages	Project documentation, including reports, technical specifications, research findings, and other relevant resources. The messages should highlight the value of the intranet in facilitating communication, knowledge exchange, and collaboration within the industrial community.
Target Audience	Members of the industrial community who are directly involved in or interested in the "MODAPTO" project, the four manufacturers comprising the MODAPTO early adopters. FFT, SEW-USOCOME (SEW), Stellantis (CRF), and ILTAR are parts of strong industrial communities with emphasis on modular manufacturing, thus having a solid potential for the broader and deeper involvement of other manufacturers, especially SMEs.
Information Required	To effectively create the industrial community intranet, it is necessary to gather information about the project documentation, demos, and other resources that will be made available to community members. Additionally, understanding the specific needs, preferences, and technical requirements

	of the target audience will inform the design and functionality of the intranet platform.
Information Provider	The project team and partners involved in the development and management of the project documentation and demos will serve as the primary information providers for this activity.
Communication Methods	The industrial community intranet can be communicated through the project's official website, newsletters, etc.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uploading and organizing project documentation, including reports, technical specifications, and research findings, in a user-friendly manner. • Creating demos and interactive resources to showcase the project's innovations and solutions. • Implementing user registration and access control mechanisms to ensure that only authorized community members can access the intranet. • Regularly updating the intranet with new project documentation, demos, and other relevant resources.
Schedule	Regular updates and maintenance should be planned to ensure that the intranet remains up-to-date and relevant.
Monitoring	Monitoring can include metrics such as the number of registered community members, frequency of document downloads, etc.
Responsible Partner	All technical partners are responsible for updating the intranet with new project documentation, etc.

4.3 Social Media

4.3.1 Twitter

Objective	MODAPTO Twitter account is used to promote the project news and related activities as well as reach a wide range of communities.
Content and Messages	Project news, events, resources, collaborations, demonstrations, publications as well as reposting the relevant social media messages.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	All actual information promoting MODAPTO findings and related information.
Information Provider	All Partners

Communication Methods	Internet
Activities	Encouraging new users to join, regularly adding new tweets and responding to comments.
Schedule	Updated on an ad-hoc basis throughout the project.
Monitoring	ATC is monitoring the account.
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for creating/operating the account. Each partner is responsible to send news to be added on Twitter.

4.3.2 LinkedIn

Objective	MODAPTO LinkedIn page is used to announce project’s achievements to other professionals from relevant fields of action, to raise questions and obtain feedback that can contribute to the project’s development. Also announce events and gather interest from other people that join our community.
Content and Messages	Project, news, events, resources, collaborations, demonstrations, publications as well as reposting the relevant social media messages
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	All actual information promoting MODAPTO findings and related information.
Information Provider	All Partners
Communication Methods	Internet
Activities	Encouraging new users to join, regularly adding new posts and responding to others' comments
Schedule	Weekly, or as we have content to add
Monitoring	ATC is monitoring the page at a minimum twice a week.
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for creating/operating the page. Each partner is responsible to send news to be added on LinkedIn.

4.3.3 YouTube

Objective	MODAPTO channel on YouTube is used to promote the project videos and related activities as well as reach a wide range of audiences.
Content and Messages	Promotional videos for the project (i.e introduction to industrial partners, use cases, explanation on identified challenges, participation on conferences, etc.)
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project concept and results
Information Provider	All Partners
Communication Methods	Internet
Activities	Encouraging new users to subscribe
Schedule	Updated on an ad-hoc basis throughout the project
Monitoring	ATC is monitoring the channel
Responsible Partner	ATC and all partners

4.4 Industrial partners' networks

Objective	Disseminate the results of new production modules with novel sustainability capabilities (analyze and optimization) and virtual commissioning tools obtained during the project. Also to disseminate the objectives and results of the application of modular DTs to the production and logistics processes, to SMEs.
Content and Messages	Results, development, business analysis, Business Impact, Future Strategies Prove the technical applicability Prove and quantify the business impact
Target Audience	Plant manager, top management, stakeholder, Plant developer and operators, SMEs in the modular manufacturing domain
Information Required	Description of all use cases with the development carried out during the project by the partner working on each use case including partner contributions.

Information Provider	CRF, ILTAR, FFT, EKS, SWE USOCOME project partners
Communication Methods	Workshops, newsletters, internal website, social media, physical meetings
Activities	Preparation of papers and presentations, Social media posts, contribution to workshops and meetings, visits in plant
Schedule	During project development, Starting 2023: 1st meeting done; linked in posts issued.
Monitoring	CRF, FFT, ILTAR, SEW USOCOME
Responsible Partner	CRF, FFT, ILTAR, SEW USOCOME

4.5 Flyers

Objective	Create a concise downloadable and printable communication material to generate maximum awareness of the project objectives and planned outcomes. The flyers should be distributed at all dissemination events, conferences, and workshops.
Content and Messages	Project's background; invitation for the Stakeholders to visit the website and join MODAPTO on social media.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objective, approach and impact, Project's main outcomes, etc.
Information Provider	ATC based on partners' contribution
Communication Methods	Written communication, face-to-face distribution, internet
Activities	Writing content, designing and printing the document
Schedule	The first flyer will be published in M7. An updated second version will be published in the second half of the project.
Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for content creation based on partners' contribution. ATC is responsible for the design.

4.6 Newsletters

Objective	To inform the audience of the latest news or updates about MODAPTO achievements, and to inform the stakeholders on the project's scope.
Content and Messages	Key project objectives, project's main results, dissemination activities, and events. The content adheres to the MODAPTO branding.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objective, approach and impact, Project's main outcomes, dissemination events and conferences attended or organised by MODAPTO, highlighted relevant news/events/conferences etc.
Information Provider	All partners
Communication Methods	Project's digital channels, list of subscribers.
Activities	Writing content, designing, editing and publishing the newsletters on MODAPTO website, promoting the newsletters on social media
Schedule	Five newsletters will be published during the project's duration (M9, M16, M24, M30, M36).
Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for content creation based on partners' contribution. ATC is responsible for the design.

4.7 International conferences and stands

Objective	Disseminate the results of MODAPTO (scientific and technical) developed in the course of the project to respective audiences. Additionally, to create lead prospects for further exploitation of the Key exploitable outcomes.
Content and Messages	Academic: Results relevant to scientific Progress beyond state of art, Impact of solution, Evaluation outcomes. Message: Prove the scientific impact of the developed solution Business: Developed system. Message: Prove the business impact upon introduction of the MODAPTO solution in the day to day operations.
Target Audience	Academic: Academic stakeholders in the different disciplines relevant to MODAPTO and respective publications. Business: Plant owners, Top management and Plant Management, SMEs in modular manufacturing domain, Standardization bodies, Policy makers
Information Required	Academic: Scientific output in the course of the project

	Business: Detailed description of the system and its impact, potential buyers
Information Provider	All partners.
Communication Methods	Academic: Abstracts/ Full Papers in international conferences, Panels, Presentations, Physical, Virtual and Hybrid presence Business: Workshops, Stands in related conferences, Banners, leaflets, Physical, Virtual and Hybrid presence
Activities	Preparation of papers, presentations, complementary communication material, F2F meetings arrangement
Schedule	During the project development, Starting 2023
Monitoring	Academic: Scientific coordinator Business: Dissemination and Communication WP leader
Responsible Partner	UL, AUEB

Table 5 below summarizes the main international events and conferences dealing with topics that are relevant to the MODAPTO project. The events list will be continuously updated by the partners and each event will be analysed for impact potential before deciding whether MODAPTO should be represented.

Table 5: Indicative Dissemination events and conferences

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience	Partner(s) Involved
IFIP International Conference - Advances in Production Management Systems (APMS)	17-21/09/2023	Trondheim, Norway	Researchers and industry practitioners in the fields of production management systems	AEGIS, AUEB
Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society (IECON)	16-19/10/2023	Singapore	Researchers, engineers, and practitioners in the field of industrial electronics.	AEGIS
EurOMA Annual Conference	3-5/07/2023	Brussels, Belgium	Academics and practitioners who have a	AEGIS

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience	Partner(s) Involved
			common interest in the continuing development of Operations Management	
POMS	Annual	Orlando, USA	Production and Operations Management professionals	AUEB
IFAC Workshop on Advanced Maintenance Engineering, Services and Technology (AMEST)	12-14/06/2024	Cagliari, Italy	International experts from academia and industry debating the latest advances in the Engineering and Management of Maintenance Systems and Services	UL
IoT Week	Postponed to 2024	TBD	IoT developers, innovators, businesses	AEGIS, AUEB
CIRP General Assembly	2025	Not yet known	The CIRP General Assembly is an annual event, globally recognized as a leading conference devoted to manufacturing engineering and attracting on the order of 700 leading international researchers.	UL
CIRP Life Cycle Engineering Conference	Annual	2024 Not yet known	CIRP has some 170 corporate members in 30 countries	UPRC, AUEB
CIRP International	24-26/10/2023	Cape Town	CIRP has some 170 corporate	UPRC, AUEB

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience	Partner(s) Involved
Conference on Manufacturing Systems (CMS)			members in 30 countries	
CIRP Conference on Modeling of Machining Operations	Annual	2024 Not yet known	CIRP has some 170 corporate members in 30 countries	UPRC, AUEB
IFAC Symposium on Information Control Problems in Manufacturing (INCOM)	2024	To be defined	Technical and Academic members and researchers	UPRC, AUEB
IFAC Manufacturing Modelling, Management and Control (MIM)	Annual	To be defined	IFAC members and International Academics and technology experts	UPRC, AUEB
European Conference of the Prognostics and Health Management Society (PHM EUROPE)	To be defined	To be defined	International experts from academia and industry debating the latest advances in the PHM domain	UL
European Conference on Operations Research (EURO)	30.6.2024-03.7.2024	Copenhagen, Denmark	Academic OR Society, >300 members from academy and industry	UPRC, AUEB
IFAC World Congress	2026	Not yet known	The IFAC World Congress is the largest event in the field of control science and technology, held every three years. It offers the most up-to-date and complete view of control techniques, with	UL

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience	Partner(s) Involved
			the widest coverage of application fields, and is attended by a worldwide audience of scientists and engineers from academia and industry.	
Industrial Transformation ASIA-PACIFIC (ITAP)	18-20/10/2023	Singapore	Leaders in manufacturing and technology sectors interested in Industry 4.0 technologies.	AEGIS
Industry of Things World	17-19/09/2023	Berlin	Industrial IoT and Industry 4.0 professionals.	AEGIS
Manufacturing Performance Days (MPD)	05-07/06/2023	Tampere, Finland	Leaders and decision-makers in the manufacturing industry	AEGIS
Annual International Conference on Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and the Internet of Things (DCOSS-IoT 2023)	19-21/06/2023	Pafos, Cyprus	Academic community of the field of distributed computing in smart systems	AUEB
25th International Conference of the Catalan Association for Artificial Intelligence (CCIA 2023)	25-27/10/2023	Món Sant Benet, Catalonia, Spain	Academic community of AI	AUEB
BALTTECHNIKA	2023 October	Vilnius, Lithuania	Industry 4.0 community	LIC

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience	Partner(s) Involved
IEEE conference on emerging technologies in automation (ETFA)	12-15/9/2023	Sinaia, Romania	Automation community	EKS

4.8 Open access publications in Scientific Journals

Objective	The objective of publishing Open Access in Scientific Journals will allow the sharing of results connected with the MODAPTO project, favoring the science progress through accessible literature to everyone.
Content and Messages	Scientific publications accessible to all either as open access publication or thanks to government platform purposed to share national research result (see for instance in France HAL (https://hal.science/#))
Target Audience	All persons interested in scientific and research results of MODAPTO project (some examples: researchers, industrial practitioners, and students).
Information Required	Scientific results of MODAPTO, advancing research in fields affected by project activities. Code and datasets may also be included.
Information Provider	All Partners contributing to the research activities in the framework of the project and publishing papers in conference, workshop and journals.
Communication Methods	The paper must be accepted by all partner for publication prior to its acceptance (see D1.1). The target journal and conference should provide open access to the paper or the paper can be made available on governmental platform (like HAL in France) if agreement exists with the editor.
Activities	Gathering information from all partners with respect to the research results achieved in the project and the connected publications.
Schedule	Key revisions at the end of each year updating the number of scientific papers achieved from the project partners in journal and conferences, and verification of the open access.
Monitoring	UL is responsible for monitoring the fact that the publications will be open access as well as metrics of publications.
Responsible Partner	UL

A preliminary list of scientific journals that will be targeted to maximize the impact of the scientific work to the target communities is presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Indicative Scientific Journals

Scientific Journal	Link (publisher)	Field	Partner(s) Involved
Reliability Engineering and System Safety	Reliability Engineering & System Safety Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Development and application of methods for the enhancement of the safety and reliability of complex technological systems	UL
Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing	Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing Home (springer.com)	Applications of artificial intelligence in manufacturing	UL
European Journal of Operational Research	European Journal of Operational Research ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Maintainability, physics of failure, life testing, prognostics, design and manufacture for reliability, reliability for systems of systems, network availability, mission success, warranty, safety, and various measures of effectiveness	AUEB, UPRC
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	IEEE Xplore: IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	Theory and application practice of informatics in industrial environments	UPRC, AUEB
International Journal of Production Research	International Journal of Production Research Taylor & Francis Online (tandfonline.com)	Manufacturing, industrial engineering, operations research and management science.	AUEB, UPRC
International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing	International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing Taylor & Francis Online (tandfonline.com)	Mechanical and manufacturing engineering, software and computer engineering as well as automation and control engineering with a particular focus on today's	AUEB,UPRC

Scientific Journal	Link (publisher)	Field	Partner(s) Involved
		data driven manufacturing	
Journal of Industrial Information Integration	Journal of Industrial Information Integration	Industry's transition towards industrial integration and informatization	UL
Journal of Cleaner Production	Journal of cleaner production	international, transdisciplinary journal focusing on Cleaner Production, Environmental, and Sustainability research and practice	UL
Computer in Industry	Computer in Industry	Use of Information and Communication Technology in industry; Link or integration of different technology fields in the broad area of computer	UL
Journal of Manufacturing Systems	Journal of Manufacturing Systems ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Fundamental and applied research in manufacturing at systems level.	AUEB, UPRC
Journal of Industrial Information Integration	Journal of Industrial Information Integration ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Industry's transition towards industrial integration and informatization	AUEB, UPRC
Production and Operations Management	Production and Operations Management - Wiley Online Library	Operations management in manufacturing and services.	UPRC, AUEB
Computers and Industrial Engineering	Computers & Industrial Engineering Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Development of new computerized methodologies for solving industrial engineering problems, as well as the applications of those methodologies to problems of interest in the broad industrial engineering and	UPRC, AUEB

Scientific Journal	Link (publisher)	Field	Partner(s) Involved
		associated communities.	

4.9 Synergies with EU Initiatives

Objective	The objective of this activity is to establish and foster collaborations and synergies with relevant European Union (EU) initiatives that align with the goals and objectives of the project. By doing so, the project aims to leverage existing resources, knowledge, and networks to enhance its impact and contribute to the broader EU framework.
Content and Messages	The content and messages for this activity will focus on highlighting the similarities, complementarities, and potential collaborative opportunities between the project's "MODAPTO" and other EU initiatives. The messages should emphasize the potential benefits of collaboration, such as knowledge exchange, increased visibility, and shared resources.
Target Audience	The primary target audience for this activity includes relevant EU initiatives, research organizations, industry associations, and key stakeholders involved in related fields such as digital manufacturing, industrial automation, and Industry 4.0. These entities should be interested in exploring synergies and collaborative opportunities to advance the objectives of their respective initiatives.
Information Required	To effectively engage with EU initiatives, it is necessary to gather information about their objectives, ongoing projects, key contacts, and areas of expertise. Additionally, understanding the project's own goals, expertise.
Information Provider	The information required for this activity can be obtained through desk research, online platforms, EU databases, and official websites of relevant EU initiatives, also through partners who are involved into other EU projects.
Communication Methods	Communication methods may include email exchanges, participation in relevant conferences, workshops, and seminars, as well as arranging one-on-one meetings with representatives of the targeted EU initiatives
Activities	Initiating contact with the identified EU initiatives through emails or formal introduction letters. Participating in conferences, workshops, and events where the targeted EU initiatives are present to establish direct communication.
Schedule	The schedule for this activity may vary depending on the availability of relevant conferences and events, as well as the responsiveness of the targeted EU initiatives
Monitoring	Keeping a record of the engagements made, meetings held, and potential collaboration opportunities identified will help evaluate the effectiveness of this activity and inform future strategies.

Responsible Partner	LIC is responsible for building and maintaining the database of EU initiatives and for initiating contact with the initiatives, so that collaboration starts with MODAPTO. All partners have to be engaged in finding the EU initiatives and establishing contacts in synergy with LIC.
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Table 7 presents an initial list of the EU initiatives that MODAPTO will try to establish and foster collaborations and synergies with.

Table 7: EU initiatives for potential synergies with MODAPTO

EU Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
A.SPIRE Association [Link]	A.SPIRE is focusing on process issues (and not really manufacturing ones as done in EFFRA) but some of these issues are closed to MODAPTO considerations (e.g., process reconfiguration)	UL
BDVA – Big Data Value Association [Link]	ATC is a founding member of the Big Data Value Association (BDVA), participates in the Board of Directors and member of Task Forces: Media, Manufacturing, Data Spaces. Guidelines and decisions of “Manufacturing” and “Data Spaces” taskforces will be communicated to MODAPTO to be taken into account. ATC will also disseminate the project results to annual or bi-annual events organized by BDVA, to highlight project accomplishments. Fraunhofer is involved in the Smart Manufacturing Industry (SMI) working group of the BDVA. Currently, Fraunhofer is co-editor of the position paper on digital twins. The results discussed in the BDVA SMI will be taken into account in the	ATC, Fraunhofer

EU Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
	<p>development of the MODAPTO DT solution and the MODAPTO challenges and results will be presented to the BDVA SMI and possibly included in future position papers.</p>	
<p>European Factories of the Future Research Association [Link]</p>	<p>The European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA) is a non-for-profit, industry-driven association promoting the development of new and innovative production technologies. It is the official representative of the private side in the "Made in Europe" partnership. So, in that way, the issues discussed in EFFRA are well in phase with MODAPTO objectives. MODAPTO must be associated to EFFRA.</p>	<p>UL, AUEB</p>
<p>HBR HORIZON Results Booster [Link]</p>	<p>With HRB's commitment to driving research towards meaningful societal impact, collaboration could ensure that MODAPTO's projects truly contribute to addressing societal challenges, leveraging the platform's services to maximize the value of Research and Innovation (R&I) activities.</p> <p>Engagement with HRB's portfolio D&E strategy could facilitate the identification, creation, and effective dissemination of MODAPTO's R&I project outcomes. By utilizing module A, partners would identify and curate a comprehensive portfolio of project results. With module B, partners would devise a</p>	<p>AEGIS</p>

EU Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
	<p>robust dissemination plan to ensure the findings are effectively communicated to key stakeholders.</p> <p>Furthermore, project’s exploitation strategy could be enhanced through the guidance of module C, thereby augmenting the overall impact of the project’s work.</p> <p>MODAPTO could also benefit immensely from the tailor-made support services offered by HRB for business plan development. This would help better structure and position the innovative outcomes for market relevance and viability.</p> <p>Moreover, the coaching and mentoring services for go-to-market activities could be invaluable in accelerating the translation of the research results into market-ready solutions.</p> <p>Specialized services provided by the HRB consortium, comprising META Group, Ecorys Europe, ICONS, Trust-IT Services, BDO, and PNO, could effectively bolster MODAPTO’s project delivery and impact. Collaboration with HRB would not only ensure exceeding the project’s D&E obligations but also foster a continuous cycle of innovation and societal impact. Through this synergy, the vision of bringing perpetual streams of innovation to the market could be actualised, drawing</p>	

EU Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
<p>AI4EU – Europe’s AI-on-demand platform [Link]</p>	<p>on project’s combined strengths and resources. Contribution of MODAPTO developed AI-related knowledge, assets, services or tools</p>	<p>UL, UPRC, ATC</p>
<p>EEN – Enterprise Europe Network [Link]</p>	<p>The EEN, with its extensive network of business support organizations, can connect Modapto with potential partners, manufacturers, and stakeholders interested in modular manufacturing and digital twin technologies. The EEN can help amplify the visibility and dissemination efforts of Modapto by taking advantage of the EEN's communication channels, events, and matchmaking activities, allowing Modapto to showcase its innovations and attract interest from potential collaborators</p>	<p>LIC</p>
<p>EIT Digital – Digital Innovation Ecosystem [Link]</p>	<p>EIT Digital organizes events, workshops, and collaborative projects that facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration among its members. Modapto can participate in these initiatives, contributing its expertise in modular manufacturing and digital twins, while also gaining insights and exposure to other digital innovation areas.</p>	<p>LIC</p>
<p>EDIH – European Digital Innovation Hubs Network [Link]</p>	<p>MODAPTO should be connected to EDIH in the way to take profit of all services offered by this digital eco-system.</p>	<p>LIC, UL</p>

4.10 Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms

Objective	The aim is to leverage local resources, expertise, and funding opportunities to enhance the project's impact and facilitate knowledge exchange.
Content and Messages	The content for this activity will emphasize the project's alignment with the objectives and priorities of relevant national or regional initiatives, funding programs, and platforms. The messages should highlight the potential benefits of collaboration, such as access to additional resources, funding opportunities, and a broader network of stakeholders.
Target Audience	National or regional government agencies, innovation hubs, industry associations, research organizations, and other stakeholders involved in supporting and promoting innovation in the field of manufacturing and digital technologies within the project's geographic scope.
Information Required	It is necessary to gather information about their objectives, funding mechanisms, eligibility criteria, key contacts, and ongoing projects
Information Provider	All partners will have to take advantage of official websites of national or regional initiatives and funding programs.
Communication Methods	Communication methods for this activity may include email exchanges, formal introduction letters, participation in relevant conferences or networking events, and arranging meetings with representatives of the targeted national or regional initiatives, funding programs, and platforms. It is also recommended to leverage digital platforms and social media to initiate and maintain communication.
Activities	Initiating contact with the identified entities through emails or formal letters, expressing interest in collaboration and requesting further information. Exploring potential funding opportunities, joint projects, and knowledge exchange activities through partnerships with the targeted entities.
Schedule	The schedule for this activity may depend on the timing of funding calls, the availability of relevant events, and the responsiveness of the targeted national or regional initiatives, funding programs, and platforms.
Monitoring	Keep a record of the engagements made, meetings held, and funding opportunities explored to evaluate the effectiveness of this activity and inform future strategies.
Responsible Partner	LIC. Also, all partners have to be involved in the activity by analysing their national, regional ecosystems, and the process will be further facilitated by LIC.

Table 8 presents an initial list of National or Regional Initiatives that MODAPTO will try to establish communication with or collaboration envisioned.

Table 8: National or Regional Initiatives for potential synergies with MODAPTO

National or Regional Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
<p>S.MART – System Manufacturing Academics Resources Technologies [Link]</p>	<p>S.MART is a French academic community to support the industry of the future requirements, creating a fertile environment by placing engineering at the service of society. S.MART federates an open academic community to build scientific, technological and societal change on a local and national scale. As such, at UL, S.MART is offering some test bed (TELMA platform) that could be used to demonstrate some development of the project.</p>	<p>UL</p>
<p>GIP – Société d’Automatique de Génie Industriel et de Productive [Link]</p>	<p>SAGIP (Société d’Automatique, de Génie Industriel et de Productive) is a French organization, mainly of academic people, whose aim is to structure and promote the disciplines in the domains of automatic control and production. engineering</p>	<p>UL</p>
<p>GdR: MACS – Groupement de recherche: Modélisation, Analyse et Conduite des Systemes Dynamiques [Link]</p>	<p>GdR MACS is a research community funded by the CNRS in France. Its main scope is to federate the research laboratories working in the fields of Modeling and Control of Dynamic Systems. Manufacturing systems is one these categories for which different working groups (WG) such as H2M, S3 are active. UL is very active in these WG investigating research issues closed to MODAPTO.</p>	<p>UL</p>
<p>GIMELEC - Groupement des entreprises de la filière</p>	<p>GIMELEC is a French trade association representing</p>	<p>SEW USOCOME</p>

National or Regional Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
<p>électronumérique française [Link]</p>	<p>210 companies that design, manufacture and deploy solutions for the electrification, decarbonisation and digital intelligence of industry, buildings, energy and digital infrastructures.</p> <p>The 4.0 theme is a major one for the group and is broken down into 9 issues: competitiveness, design, continuity, digitalisation, eco-responsibility, efficiency, integration, security and societal issues.</p> <p>The aim will be to share the results of Modapto to inform the group's companies of the effects of modularity controlled by the digital twin.</p>	
<p>Artema – Le Syndicat des industriels de la Mecatronique [Link]</p>	<p>ARTEMA is a trade association for mechatronics companies in France. ARTEMA has around 150 member companies throughout France and 35,000 employees. The aim is to promote innovation and collaboration between research and industry.</p>	<p>SEW USOCOME</p>
<p>VDI – Verein Deutscher Ingenieure e.V. [Link]</p>	<p>Exchange and adaptation of standards provided by the VDI.</p>	<p>EKS</p>
<p>CATENA-X - Catena-X Automotive Network [Link]</p>	<p>The MODAPTO project will take into account the results of the CATENA-X "Modular Production" WP. It is not expected that the MODAPTO results will be used in CATENA-X, as the MODAPTO technical WPs will start in M8</p>	<p>Fraunhofer</p>

National or Regional Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
	<p>when the CATENA-X project will enter the test and evaluation phase. However, there is the possibility of influencing the CATENA-X results in future projects, e.g., the FACTORY-X project.</p>	
<p>OMiLAB - Conceptual modelling community [Link]</p>	<p>The meta-models provided by the OMiLAB community will be evaluated and, when needed, integrated in MODAPTO. Their potential extension and adaptation in the MODAPTO project will then be shared and made available to the OMiLAB community.</p>	<p>BOC</p>
<p>Corallia Clusters Initiative [Link]</p>	<p>Corallia focuses on improving the competitiveness, business and technological performance of Greek firms by inspiring and promoting cooperation among its members and international counterparts. Corallia's focus on innovation and cooperation in high-tech sectors aligns well with MODAPTO's goals. Corallia can help spread MODAPTO's technology among Greek firms and encourage collaborations.</p>	<p>AEGIS</p>
<p>Industry 4.0 Initiative [Link]</p>	<p>The Industry 4.0 initiative is a national strategic initiative by the German government which aims to drive digital manufacturing forward. Both Industry 4.0 and MODAPTO are focused on digital transformation in manufacturing. MODAPTO could contribute to and benefit from the advancements promoted by the Industry 4.0 initiative.</p>	<p>AEGIS</p>

4.11 Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects

Objective	The objective of clustering activities is to increase the technical and social impact of the MODAPTO results on European level; this will be possible thanks to the collaboration and technical discussions with other EU projects.
Content and Messages	Project’s background, progress and news, value of networks for capacity building
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Information related to the other EU projects involved in the clustering activities.
Information Provider	Stakeholders of other EU projects identified by the partners of MODAPTO project
Communication Methods	MODAPTO website; common workshop
Activities	Gathering documentation and information to keep trace of the clustering activities performed in the MODAPTO project by all partners.
Schedule	Key revisions every six months updating the collaboration activities along the project.
Monitoring	UL is responsible for monitoring the clustering and connection activities with other EU projects.
Responsible Partner	UL

Table 9 presents the list of the Horizon Europe projects funded under the same topic (HORIZON_HORIZON-CL4-2022-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-03) that MODAPTO will seek to establish communication with or collaboration is envisioned.

Table 9: Horizon Europe Projects related to MODAPTO

Horizon Europe Project	Expected areas of collaboration
MARS Manufacturing Architecture for Resilience and Sustainability (Link)	Special and invited sessions at international and national conferences and workshops can be organized jointly.
MODUL4R Industrial Manufacturing strategies for distributed control and resilient, rapidly responsive and reconfigurable supply chains (Link)	Special and invited sessions at international and national conferences and workshops can be organized jointly.

ONE4ALL Agile and modular cyber-physical technologies supported by data-driven digital tools to reinforce manufacturing resilience (Link)	Special and invited sessions at international and national conferences and workshops can be organized jointly.
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4.12 Training-demos

Objective	To develop and make available online training materials and specific demos related to the MODAPTO project. The aim is to provide valuable resources to interested parties, including stakeholders, professionals, researchers, and the broader community, to enhance their understanding and practical knowledge of the project's concepts, technologies, and lessons learned.
Content and Messages	Providing comprehensive and accessible training materials and specific demos that showcase the project's innovations, best practices, and practical applications. The messages should emphasize the educational value, relevance, and potential benefits of utilizing the provided resources.
Target Audience	Professionals, researchers, students, industry practitioners, and other individuals interested in gaining knowledge and insights into modular manufacturing, distributed control, and digital twins. The training materials and demos should be designed to cater to different levels of expertise and accommodate a wide range of interested parties.
Information Required	The project's key concepts, technologies, methodologies, and lessons learned will be derived from project reports, case studies, research findings, and the expertise of project partners.
Information Provider	The information required for this activity will be provided by the project team, including subject matter experts, researchers, and partners involved in the project.
Communication Methods	Communication methods for this activity will primarily involve online channels and platforms to ensure broad accessibility and reach. The training materials and demos can be made available through a dedicated project website, video hosting platforms, social media channels, and relevant industry forums.
Activities	Identifying the key training topics and demos based on the project's objectives and lessons learned. Developing engaging and informative training materials, such as presentations, video tutorials, e-learning modules, and practical demos. Organizing the content in a structured and easily navigable manner on the project website or online learning platforms. Promoting the availability of the training materials and demos through social media, newsletters, and relevant industry events.
Schedule	The schedule for this activity should consider the development and refinement of the training materials and demos based on the project's timeline and milestones.

Monitoring	LIC. Monitoring the progress of this activity involves tracking the usage and feedback of the training materials and demos.
Responsible Partner	LIC. All research and industry partners will assist the creation of training material and training demos by providing related content and information. LIC will be further responsible for curating, and maintaining the training materials and demos.

4.13 Workshops and demonstrations

Objective	To showcase the technologies and solutions developed by the project partners in the context of MODAPTO. The aim is to provide hands-on experience and practical insights to industry partners, stakeholders, and interested parties, highlighting the project's innovations and their potential applications.
Content and Messages	Demonstrating the capabilities, functionalities, and benefits of the technologies and solutions developed by the project partners. The messages should emphasize the practical value, real-world applicability, and potential impact of implementing these innovations in the manufacturing and control domain.
Target Audience	Industry community, professionals, EDIHs, researchers and other individuals or organizations interested in adopting or collaborating on advanced manufacturing technologies.
Information Required	Specification about the technologies, solutions, and use cases developed by the project partners.
Information Provider	The project partners involved in the development of the technologies and solutions will serve as the primary information providers for this activity.
Communication Methods	A combination of onsite and online channels. Onsite workshops and demonstrations can be organized at one of the industry partner's facilities, while online platforms can be utilized to reach a broader audience and enable remote participation. This can include live streaming, webinars, and interactive Q&A sessions.
Activities	Identifying the specific technologies, solutions, and use cases to be showcased during the workshops and demonstrations. Coordinating with industry partners to select an appropriate venue or facility for the onsite demonstrations. Developing a structured agenda and format for the workshops, including presentations, hands-on sessions, and interactive discussions. Creating informative and visually appealing materials, such as brochures, presentations, videos, and technical documentation, to support the demonstrations.

	Promoting the workshops and demonstrations through targeted invitations, online announcements, and collaboration with industry networks or associations.
Schedule	On the second half of the project, when technology will be ready for demonstrations. The schedule for this activity should consider the availability of the industry partner's facility for onsite demonstrations
Monitoring	LIC. Monitoring will be done via feedback surveys, post-event evaluations, and direct interactions with the participants. These can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness, relevance, and impact of the demonstrations.
Responsible Partner	LIC will be responsible for organizing and executing the workshops and demonstrations. All partners will contribute by providing specifications about the technologies, solutions, and also the partners who will host the demonstrations will be indicated.

4.14 Articles in printed/online media (not scientific)

Objective	To disseminate and communicate the MODAPTO platform and benefits. To produce white papers showcasing the process to apply MODAPTO and modular manufacturing in different industrial settings.
Content and Messages	Demonstration of different business cases their process to introduce MODAPTO offering in their day-to-day activities and in a broader strategic manner. Messages utilized will focus on showcasing the envisaged and evaluated benefits post MODAPTO application
Target Audience	Industry community, plant owners, developers
Information Required	Specification about MODAPTO, Impact of MODAPTO
Information Provider	All technical partners involved in the development of the solution.
Communication Methods	Project's digital channels.
Activities	Identification of relevant online and offline outlets eligible for contribution, Communication of articles, Authoring of white papers
Schedule	Technical white papers on the second half of the project after development of MODAPTO system. Periodic contribution of various tangible results as they progressively emerge to specific outlets
Monitoring	UPRC. Follow-up of the articles published, cross-publication and monitoring of the availability of white-papers produced.

Responsible Partner	UPRC. All technical partners for the provision of content.
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4.15 Student conferences

Objective	To disseminate the MODAPTO outcomes to current students and prospective professionals in the field.
Content and Messages	MODAPTO can present progress in various fields which will be common practice in the manufacturing of the future and as such early exposure to future professionals is proposed
Target Audience	Students at undergraduate levels, Students at post-graduate levels
Information Required	Scientific and technical outputs of MODAPTO in the form of Abstracts and full papers
Information Provider	All partners providing tangible results of their project activities.
Communication Methods	Through the organization bodies of each conference and also MODAPTO website, MODAPTO Social Media.
Activities	Present ongoing research, Conduct panels
Schedule	Annual
Monitoring	AUEB, ATC
Responsible Partner	AUEB, UPRC

4.16 Press Releases

Objective	To raise awareness within the widest audience about the project
Content and Messages	Brief summary of the project, the challenges it addresses, its main objectives and partners involved
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objectives, approach and impact, as well as all project partners' names

Information Provider	ATC to be revised by all partners
Communication Methods	Internet, MODAPTO website, partners' contacts and network
Activities	Writing content, designing, editing the press releases in English language. Replication of press releases in languages of the consortium countries by all partners at regional/national level, in order to leverage project coverage by reaching out to non-English speaking audiences. Publishing of the press releases on MODAPTO website. Promoting/emailing press releases on partners' networks.
Schedule	Three times during the project period: after project start to raise awareness within the widest audience about the project; at project midterm to inform on first achievements and tangible benefits; and at project end or shortly after it to promote project results.
Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	ATC. All partners to translate the Press releases to local languages, so as to replicate the activity to regional/national level.

4.17 Video

Objective	To showcase the project concept and results.
Content and Messages	A brief explainer video on MODAPTO concept, objectives and results.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objectives, approach and main outcomes.
Information Provider	ATC with contribution from partners
Communication Methods	Project's digital channels
Activities	Writing script, editing and production, publishing the video on the website and promoting the video on social media. Showcasing the video in different project presentations and events.
Schedule	Between M12-M18 of the project.

<i>Monitoring</i>	ATC
<i>Responsible Partner</i>	All partners as content providers, ATC is responsible for final scripting and rendering.

5 Visual Identity

Early in the development of the project, and in order to pursue the establishment of a strong visual identity that will help MODAPTO project to achieve its potential impact, the project identity kit was produced, including the project branding and templates for internal and external materials.

5.1 Logo

The logo has been created to sign off the project’s identity, and to be applied on all communication collaterals and outlets (see Figure 2 and Figure 3). Including the website, the project’s templates, its social media profiles, and more. It is also available for downloading on the project’s website in the link [here](#).

Figure 2: MODAPTO logo – basic version

Figure 3: MODAPTO logo - alternative versions

Alternative colour variations of the logo, applicable to different background, have been also created (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: MODAPTO logo - versions adapting to different backgrounds

The logo was designed according to the project’s vision on flexible industrial systems composed of modules enhanced by distributed intelligence via interoperable Digital Twins (DTs) based on industrial standards.

The logo consists of the project’s acronym (MODAPTO), depicted in capital letters. The acronym actually occurs as a synthesis of

- the syllable “MO”, representing for the word “Modular” (Composed of standardized units for flexible arrangement);
- the letter D, which stands for Distributed (Spread out, not concentrated in one place), which is actually depicted in the form of a red colored gear (cut in half), representing manufacturing industry, combined with an abstract icon representing digital twins notion;
- the latin word “Apto”, which stands for “Fasten, fit, apply, adjust, accommodate, prepare”.

All these elements represent the emphasis the project is placing on the idea of modular, distributed and adjustable manufacturing systems.

5.2 Colour palette

MODAPTO uses the following colour palette as shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: MODAPTO colour palette

There are two main colours, that constitute the original logo, and two complementary ones, to allow a full colour palette used in visuals and templates. The project's colour scheme was carefully chosen so that it is appealing to the targeted audience. In addition, all colours have been selected to work well in combination with each other and to enable a full range of visually engaging communications.

The project's "acronym" (MODAPTO) is depicted in "Cosmic Cobalt" (Hex 2C3687, RGB 44, 54, 135), a popular darker shade of blue. It was selected due to its "industrial" origins (in general, the cobalt color is the result of cobalt monoxide and alumina being manipulated, compressed and heated in such a way that results in the cobalt pigment).

The specific cool-toned blue is also associated with modernity, technology, and calmness. Furthermore, the slightly purple undertone in #2C3687 adds a touch of creativity and individuality to the color, suggesting a blend of professionalism and creative expression.

Last but not least, the looming gear in the middle of the logo, is depicted in a deep, vibrant red (Hex BF2227, RGB 191, 34, 39), similar to "Red Carpet" shade. This rich tone intensifies the emotional impact of the color and aims to convey a sense of strength and vigor, alongside the project team's aim to produce credible results.

Overall, the project's team resulted this visually striking and powerful color combination to communicate a message of trustworthy excitement, reliable energy and professional passion, or, in other words, a balance between dynamic, passionate elements and a foundation of stability, reliability, and expertise.

5.3 Display of EU funding information

All MODAPTO communication or dissemination materials must display the EU funding information, including the EU emblem and the funding statement (as shown in Figure 6 below).

Figure 6: EU Emblem and funding statement

Moreover, all materials produced must indicate the following disclaimer:

"This project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101061516. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

5.4 Brand guide

A complete MODAPTO brand guide featuring the logo and its use, the colour scheme, typography, imagery, brand elements etc. was developed and shared with all consortium partners. It should be followed across all dissemination and communication activities.

Figure 7: MODAPTO brand guide (screenshots)

5.5 Document templates

The following templates have been created according to the MODAPTO visual identity and clearly show the EU funding information:

- Word Document – Deliverable template
- PowerPoint – Presentation Template

All consortium partners will adopt the templates provided to maintain visual coherency throughout the project.

Figure 8: MODAPTO Deliverable template (screenshots)

Figure 9: MODAPTO PowerPoint template (screenshots)

More templates for internal materials of the project (Agenda, Minutes, Peer Review Report etc.) have been also created following the guidelines of the logo design and have been presented in deliverable “D1.1- Project Handbook, Quality Plan”.

5.6 Visuals

Several visuals have been prepared to present the project on social media using the MODAPTO visual identity. The project logo is present in every visual to maintain coherency throughout all communication efforts.

Figure 10: MODAPTO visuals – example

5.6.1 The gear as a basic branding element

Using the gear as a key element of the project's visual identity is based on:

- **representation of industry and manufacturing**, since they are mechanical components used in machinery and equipment, symbolizing precision, mechanical power, and engineering. Incorporating the gear in the project's logo aimed to convey that the project is involved in manufacturing, engineering, or related industries.
- **symbolizing movement and progress**, since gears work together to transmit power and create movement. They represent the idea of progress, teamwork, and collaboration. Using a gear in the project's logo also symbolizes its dynamic nature and the project's team's emphasis on collective efforts to drive progress.
- **implying efficiency and precision**, since gears are designed to mesh and rotate with minimal friction, enabling smooth and efficient mechanical operations. By incorporating the gear in our logo, the consortium actually wishes to suggest its commitment to efficiency, precision, and high-quality work, promoting its attention to detail and accuracy.

6 Dissemination & Communication Time-plan

As shown in previous chapters of this document, the dissemination and communication strategy of MODAPTO is based on three phases:

- Phase I: Inform & Connect
- Phase II: Demonstrate & Contribute
- Phase III: Share & Convince

Within these three phases, there are different aspects to address. Figure 11 is a short overview of important deadlines and actions that will play a big role in the dissemination and communication of MODAPTO.

Figure 11: Dissemination and Communication Time plan

Table 10 below outlines the plans for key activities foreseen at the first year of the project.

Table 10: Dissemination & Communication Time plan for Year 1

Delivery Date	Activity	Remark	Status	Lead/Contributors
M3	Project Identity Kit	Project branding, Templates for internal/external material, Guidelines for partners	Delivered	ATC

Delivery Date	Activity	Remark	Status	Lead/Contributors
M3	Project website	Creation and maintenance	Delivered	ATC
M3	Social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)	Creation and maintenance	Delivered	ATC
M6	Press Release	Compilation of First Issue	Delivered	ATC
M6	Dissemination and Communication strategy (D2.1)	Compilation and submission	Delivered	ATC with contribution from partners
M6	Dissemination and Communication Monitoring	Creation	Delivered	ATC
M7	Flyer	Creation	Planned	ATC with contribution from partners
M9	Newsletter	Creation of First Issue	Planned	ATC with contribution from partners

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

7.1 Quantitative & Qualitative Evaluation of MODAPTO Dissemination and Communication

In accordance with the evaluation criteria and indicators for measurement of the level of success of dissemination and communication activities, the qualitative and quantitative aspects of evaluation will be examined in detail in the following paragraphs.

In order to capture the effectiveness of dissemination and communication, a combination of criteria or feedback mechanisms is being used to measure the effectiveness of each dissemination and communication activity. The project has developed an online monitoring template, which all partners are using in order to register and monitor their activities. Information to be contained in this template is as following:

For Publications

<i>Type of PID¹ (repository)</i>	Choose from the list: DOI, Handle, ARK, URI, Purl, Other, None
<i>PID (publisher version of record)</i>	Insert PID reference (PID -Publisher version of record is the one assigned to the publication by the publisher)
<i>PID of deposited publication</i>	Insert PID reference (PID of deposited publication is the PID that the published manuscript or the final peer-reviewed version takes when deposited to the open repository)
<i>Type of publication</i>	Choose from the list: Article in Journal, Publication in conference proceeding/workshop, Books/monographs, Chapters in books, Thesis/dissertation, Other
<i>Link to publication</i>	The link should be added only if PID/DOI is not available
<i>Title of the scientific publication</i>	Insert title of the publication. If it is a book chapter please add the title of the chapter, not the title of the book
<i>Authors</i>	Insert author names. The name of the authors should be complete only if PID/DOI is not available
<i>Title of the journal or equivalent</i>	Insert the title of the journal (in case of a book, please look below)
<i>Number</i>	Insert the number of journal

¹ PID: persistent identifier

ISSN or eISSN	Insert ISSN/ eSSN number. If book insert ISBN.
Publisher	Insert name of the publisher
Month of publication	Insert month of publication
Year of publication	Insert year of publication
Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	Choose from the list: Yes, No
Peer-reviewed	Choose from the list: Yes, No
PID of Book	Insert PID reference if book chapter
Book title	Insert book title if book chapter
Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Choose from the list: Yes, No
Type of publishing venue	Choose from the list: Hybrid venue, Full open access venue, Full subscription venue (only if OA publishing fees are charged to the project) <i>Note: APCs/BPCs paid to hybrid publishing venues are non-eligible costs under Horizon Europe</i>
Article processing costs that will be charged to the project	Type the amount in (€)

For Dissemination Activities

Partner Organisation	Choose from the list: ATC, Fraunhofer, UL, UPRC, AUEB, EKS, BOC, AEGIS, LIC, FFT, SEW USOCOME, CRF, ILTAR
Responsible Person	Fill in the cell with the name(s) of the person(s) who will be responsible for gathering input for the dissemination activity.

<i>Other partners involved</i>	Indicate one or more partners: ATC, Fraunhofer, UL, UPRC, AUEB, EKS, BOC, AEGIS, LIC, FFT, SEW USOCOME, CRF, ILTAR
<i>Dissemination activity name</i>	Insert activity name
<i>Type of Dissemination activity</i>	Choose from the list: Conferences, Education and training events, Meetings, Clustering activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Other scientific collaboration, Other
<i>Target audience reached</i>	Choose from the list an audience: Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators, Investors, International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.), EU Institutions, National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Specific end user communities, Other
<i>Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output</i>	Using max 200 characters, insert description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output
<i>Status of the dissemination activity</i>	Choose from the list: Cancelled, Delivered, Ongoing, Postponed

For Communication Activities

<i>Partner Organisation</i>	Choose from the list: ATC, Fraunhofer, UL, UPRC, AUEB, EKS, BOC, AEGIS, LIC, FFT, SEW USOCOME, CRF, ILTAR
<i>Responsible Person</i>	Fill in the cell with the name(s) of the person(s) who will be responsible for gathering input for the communication activity.
<i>Other partners involved</i>	Indicate one or more partners: ATC, Fraunhofer, UL, UPRC, AUEB, EKS, BOC, AEGIS, LIC, FFT, SEW USOCOME, CRF, ILTAR
<i>Communication Activity Name</i>	Insert communication name
<i>Description</i>	Insert description of implemented communication activity
<i>Target audience</i>	Choose from the list: Citizens, Civil society, EU Institutions, Industry, business partners, Innovators, International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.), Investors, Local authorities, National authorities, Regional authorities, Research communities, Specific user communities (if applicable)

Communication channel	Choose from the list: Event (including conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.), Exhibition, Interview, Media article, Newsletter, Press release, Printed materials (including brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.), Social media, TV/Radio, Campaign, Video, Website, Other
Outcome	Insert key performance indicators
Status	Choose from the list: Cancelled, Delivered, Ongoing, Postponed

For every blog post on MODAPTO website, the needed information to be filled in is as follows:

Title	Title of the blog post
Description	The main text of the blog post
Resources	Indication of (links to) presentations, photographs, or other relative material

For measuring effectiveness of the online communication, the following metrics must be compiled on a monthly basis, by the responsible partner:

Website	Google Analytics has been integrated into the web page to collect generic analytics information such as users-visitors, sessions, average session duration, page views, new visitors, and returning visitors.
Social Media	Number of followers, number of tweets/posts, impressions/reach, link clicks

Table 11 below presents a list of target values for quantitative indicators based on which the dissemination and communication impact of the project will be evaluated.

Table 11: MODAPTO Dissemination and Communication quantitative indicators

Project website	≥1.000 visits/year
Industrial community intranet	≥500 downloads of project docs and demos
Social Media	≥100 Posts/year, ≥500 Followers

<i>Industrial partners' networks</i>	≥5 events and presentations
<i>Flyers and newsletters</i>	≥5 newsletters; ≥2 flyers
<i>International conferences and stands</i>	>20 conferences and stands
<i>Open access publications in Scientific Journals</i>	>7 Papers in Top Scientific Journals
<i>Synergies with EU Initiatives</i>	≥ 10 EU Initiatives
<i>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</i>	≥10 national or regional initiatives
<i>Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects</i>	3 projects
<i>Training - demos</i>	>10 Training material & targeted demos
<i>Workshops and demonstrations</i>	>3 workshops
<i>Articles in printed/online media</i>	≥3 articles
<i>Student conferences</i>	≥1 event
<i>Press releases</i>	At least 3 press releases in English
<i>Video</i>	≥1 video

The qualitative aspects of dissemination and communication are closely related to the main project objectives that are to be attained and how these dissemination and communication activities will be successful in supporting them. This deliverable contains an account of:

- What will be produced and presented from the point of dissemination and communication?
- How, when and where will it be presented and distributed?
- To whom will the results be disseminated?
- Who will participate?

7.2 Expected Impact

The outcomes of MODAPTO dissemination and communication activities should ensure a positive impact in the domain of Digital twins for business optimisation and modular manufacturing. Moreover, MODAPTO is expected to be extremely beneficial for various target groups that are defined not only by their direct interest in the project results as potential users (for example Manufacturing Companies, SMEs, industrial associations, ICT companies) but also by their institutional and scientific status (i.e. universities and scientific community).

The impact of dissemination and communication will be analyzed based on several aspects that need to be taken into account such as:

Inputs	The resources to be used for reaching the objectives
Activities	The dissemination and communication activities to be performed
Outputs	The direct results of activities - a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators to measure outputs
Outcomes	Longer-term effects on the people, communities, or domains
Impact	The impact may be estimated after a deeper investigation and longer-term assessment, and based on the evaluation of all previous components

7.3 Impact in Relation to Objectives

Table 12 below summarizes the original dissemination & communication objectives and how the project aims to deliver impact.

Table 12: Impact in relation to dissemination and communication objectives

Original Dissemination & Communication Objectives	How MODAPTO Delivers Impact
Provide visibility and public awareness of the project by following a strategy targeting the critical actors in the broader European community and national public bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composition of a project identity kit that is appealing to target audiences; • Uses online channels to reach experts and non-experts alike; • Publication of communication material (flyers, newsletters, press releases, video etc.)
Publish results in international industrial and academic conferences, workshops and journals to inform the relevant interested third parties (academic/research and private/public organisations) about MODAPTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications (in journals and conferences), participation to relative events (conferences, workshops, etc.);

Original Dissemination & Communication Objectives	How MODAPTO Delivers Impact
<p>Support cluster collaboration and cross-pollination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies EU Initiatives and national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms for collaboration • Clustering activities to exploit synergies between other projects financed under the same topic and increase their impact. Common areas of collaboration will be agreed, similar technology needs will be identified, and common dissemination channels and activities will be scheduled.
<p>Promote SME engagement and provide workforce and trainers' training for knowledge transfer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of workshops and demonstrations

7.4 Risks & Issues related to Dissemination and Communication

The main risks related to the dissemination and communication side of the project is presented in Table 13 below. These risks, as well as any other identified risk or potential issue related to dissemination and communication, will be monitored and mitigated by the Project Coordinator. However, the WP2 Leader will also examine these risks on a regular basis and report any changes to the Project Coordinator.

Table 13: Risks related to Dissemination and Communication

Risk Statement	Level of Impact	Mitigating Measures
<p>Reluctance from partners to conduct dissemination and communication actions</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>Clearly defined communication and dissemination roles and trajectories of partners (Academics focus on Academic publications, Technical focus on Business related communication and dissemination actions).</p>
<p>Communication and Dissemination actions fail to meet the relevant KPIs.</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Partners will follow the Dissemination and Communication strategy and plan of MODAPTO. The PC in coordination with the WP leader (AUEB) will monitor the evolution (and performance) of dissemination and communication actions</p>

Risk Statement	Level of Impact	Mitigating Measures
		and propose additional targeted activities.

8 Partners’ Roles & Responsibilities

To ensure that all project partners have a clear understanding of their dissemination and communication responsibilities, this section will outline the key roles for dissemination/communication activities. Each partner is responsible for undertaking dissemination activities within their networks and for communicating the project at any relevant events that they attend. The individual dissemination and communication activities per partner are presented as follows.

ATC is leading Task 2.1 “Communication, Industrial and Scientific Dissemination” of WP2 “Dissemination, Exploitation, Business & Knowledge Transfer” and will oversee the planning, execution, monitoring, and reporting of project dissemination and communication activities. ATC will be responsible for the definition of the overall dissemination and communication strategy, with the support from the rest of the consortium. Moreover, ATC is responsible for the creation and maintenance of the various online channels (project website and social media) that will be used to communicate the project results, as well as for the production of the project identity kit and content to support the communication of the project. Additionally, ATC will actively communicate project objectives and results through its network of partners and established distribution channels towards its customer base as well as multiply the visibility of the project’s activities and results via each own online channel (website, social media).

Fraunhofer will disseminate the results of MODAPTO to national and international research communities, i.e. at conferences, workshops or in journals on the area of digital twins in order to maximize the impact of the project on the scientific community. Additionally, the results of the project will be disseminated among regional and national partners and companies. In the first year of the project, the industrial-related activities will focus on “in-house” lab demonstrators, presentations of the project results to industrial partners and demonstrations in the Karlsruhe research factory. Towards the end of the project, the MODAPTO results will be presented at large fairs, where Fraunhofer IOSB usually has its own booth (e.g., Hannover Messe or SPS). Finally, Fraunhofer IOSB will disseminate the results of the MODAPTO project in the relevant communities, e.g. BVDA SMI.

UL will perform dissemination activities mainly through the publication of scientific papers in international journals, conferences, and workshops (open access or available through HAL portal). Also, social media channels could be used, as LinkedIn and Twitter, for communication and dissemination activities. As SC, UL will monitor and promote open access publication.

UPRC as a University will conduct dissemination activities by pursuing publications of scientific papers in peer reviewed journals and conferences as well as participate in the creation of white papers all in the field of Optimization and in general Operations Research. Furthermore it will examine the creation of a spin-off (in collaboration with AUEB) towards bringing MODAPTO’s optimization solution in the market. Furthermore, it will use its own outlets for disseminating and communicating MODAPTO outputs in terms of news, updates and white papers.

AUEB as a University will support exploitation aspects by (i) providing entrepreneurial support to the other partners or researchers that wish to establish spin-offs in order take the project results to the market, AUEB has affiliation with the Athens Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation (ACEIn) which provides the relative services to selected spin-offs from MODAPTO research (ii) expanding vertical expertise in optimization and design of electronic services (for the optimization engine) and (iii) contributing to the development of relevant educational resources to be used in both general and specialized courses at undergraduate, postgraduate levels as well managerial lifelong learning (online and offline) in related fields to the AUEB role in the field.

EKS will perform dissemination and communication activities mainly through internal company presentation, presentation of results to customers of EKS, exhibition of the results at trade fairs, publications on scientific papers, presentation of results at conferences as well as dissemination of results via social media channels of EKS.

BOC will disseminate and communicate the results of MODAPTO project in the OMiLAB community, and the ADOxx Community, composed of more than 5500 users in the (meta-) modelling domain.

AEGIS will actively contribute to the dissemination and communication activities for the MODAPTO project, aligning its strategy with the project's objectives and interests. Leveraging the power of social media and various digital channels, AEGIS will share insights about the project's advancements, research activities, and notable achievements. This will include the publication of engaging content, such as informative blog posts that encapsulate the core objectives and the unique value proposition of MODAPTO. Moreover, AEGIS will support representation of MODAPTO in relevant industry workshops, conferences, and forums, showcasing the project's innovative solutions and fostering dialogue around its potential impact on modular manufacturing. By contributing to these events. This multi-faceted approach to dissemination and communication will ensure MODAPTO's visibility, engagement, and impact, amplifying the project's influence within and beyond the manufacturing sector.

LIC will actively engage in social media, participate in national and EU events to present project activities and results, and seek out collaborations with similar initiatives to enhance the dissemination and impact of the MODAPTO project.

FFT intends to present achieved results of MODAPTO to FFT customers as well as using the FFT network for dissemination through presentations, workshops and conferences. Main topics for dissemination of results will be the use of digital twins in body-in-white manufacturing processes and the sustainable use of production resources. The content as well as the dissemination can be carried out on a regional, national as well as international level depending on the target. Dissemination and communication during the project will be on a regional or national level using presentations and demonstrations. FFT also plans communication and dissemination activities via social platforms as well as FFT website and FFT Intranet. Together with project partners, further activities through publications at trade fairs or through scientific contributions are conceivable, but not further specified.

SEW USOCOME will disseminate MODAPTO results within the SEW Group and SEW USOCOME customers, the GIMELEC network (GIMELEC is a French trade association representing 210 companies that design, manufacture, and deploy solutions for the electrification,

decarbonization and digital intelligence of industry, buildings, energy and digital infrastructures), the ARTEMA network (ARTEMA is the professional organization of mechatronics manufacturers. ARTEMA brings together 150 companies throughout France - SMEs, ETIs and groups) as well as the RESILIAN network (regional network of innovative industrialists in northern Alsace). In addition, SEW USOCOME will distribute MODAPTO results via press releases to regional and national media (specialized or general information) and will disseminate the project through conferences, newsletters, and social network.

CRF pilot case will be tested mainly in the CRF's premises, but also showcased and eventually tested in some Stellantis' plant. This will prepare an internal acknowledgement of the MODAPTO technology and related demonstrator relevant for stronger exploitation. The internal dissemination/exploitation procedure by CRF in Stellantis of newly developed technologies starts usually from an internal presentation of the developed technologies made with internal stakeholders (plant and shop-floors managers, inno-leaders and experts) followed by a showcase activity in a potentially interested reference site. Results of the testing are further internally investigated in Stellantis development stages and afterward diffused among plants at worldwide level. The Stellantis group has around 100 plants and internal dissemination can reach experts worldwide with a strong European focus (Italy, France, Spain, Portugal, Germany, Poland, Czech Republic, Austria, Serbia, Slovakia, United Kingdom) for other inside to further Stellantis group at worldwide level. CRF will thus start the process with preliminary meetings with the reference inno-leaders of PWT, Electrification (Battery Hub, Sustain Era Circular Economy HUB, vehicle assembly...). Besides the internal dissemination approach, CRF intends to present relevant achievement, participating to conferences, fairs and further showcasing the results toward relevant partners and suppliers in the supplier's network. Furthermore, CRF prepares an internal diffusion e-book with a yearly two-page of each CRF's project. The e-book is available exclusively on the Stellantis intranet and accessible only to targeted people, but guarantees a wide, relevant access to the information. CRF will also support project's collective dissemination, exploitation or other communication, workshops, participation to conferences whenever possible with its own participation and expertise.

ILTAR will disseminate and communicate the results of MODAPTO project inside its own network (Piedmont SMEs associations). In addition, ILTAR will distribute MODAPTO results via press releases to regional and national media and will disseminate the project through presentations, workshops, newsletters and social media.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable is part of WP2 “Dissemination, Exploitation, Business & Knowledge Transfer” and provides information regarding the dissemination and communication strategy as well as the plan to raise awareness, share knowledge, attract potential stakeholders. This document presents an overview of the targeted audiences and identifies the channels, tools and activities to be used in order to disseminate and communicate the project’s results.

Moreover, relevant dissemination events and scientific journals that are found suitable for presenting the project and promoting its goals have been identified. In addition, EU Initiatives and national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms that synergies are envisioned as well as other EU projects for collaboration are listed. All these aspects are important and essential for the impact of project results and to ensure that the whole consortium will try to do as most as possible to make third parties aware of the project outcomes. The proposed dissemination and communication activities will be continuously monitored and accordingly updated, so this deliverable provided an overview of what is known and planned at the time of writing this document.